

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Happiness and people's perception towards Indian stand-up and comedy shows: An analytical study of Delhi

Ajay Kumar *, Sofiya Khan and Tanushka Soni

Department of Political Science, Ramanujan College, University of Delhi, Delhi, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(02), 814–824

Publication history: Received on 06 January 2023; revised on 18 February 2023; accepted on 21 February 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.2.0280>

Abstract

Indian stand-up and comedy shows are popular sources of entertainment and provide happiness which may be defined as funny programs on national TV channels or YouTube. Comedy is considered an art and known as one of the most powerful forms of expression for telling the truth to power. In India, personal, societal, and political satire-related stand-up and comedy shows are highly popular. According to World Happiness Report 2022, India got 136th rank which is tenth from the bottom of the list. It means Indians may have many problems in their day-to-day life such as illness, disease, a stressful workload, and many others. So, to escape from stressful life it is significant to remember the universal desire for happiness and in such circumstances, stand-up and comedy shows may be considered more valuable in India. That is why people have become dependent on comedy shows on TV or stand-up comedy shows on YouTube channels in the pro-technological era to attain happiness. Most people prefer to watch these shows online and offline, on the other hand most of them dislike the same due to the serving of vulgarity, titillation, sexuality, sexual abuse, body shaming, obscenity, casteist comments, etc. in these stand-up and comedy shows by which a clean comedy is getting decline. Therefore, knowing the perception of people has become a serious issue for investigation. A sample of Delhi-based people was selected for the study and a survey was applied to determine the factors that predict the perception of the people regarding stand-up and comedy shows in India in terms of their happiness.

Keywords: Comedy shows; Comment; Double-meaning; Happiness; Jokes; Perception; Standup

1. Introduction

Stand-up and comedy shows are popular forms of entertainment. Many people seem to really enjoy them and often watch them on TV /YouTube or like to watch them live. In recent years these shows have become increasingly plausible in India. This is likely due to the fact that they offer a much-needed respite from the day-to-day stresses of workload and other obligations. Therefore, people are always looking for a break from the real world to attain happiness. In fact, a study of 2016 showed that individuals who watch comedy shows are happier than those who don't [1]. Despite this, some people are not a fan of these shows due to their own reasons as they find them 'vulgar', casteist/ racist, offensive, abusive, and sometimes a waste of time. People have different perceptions towards these shows. However, most people believe that these kinds of shows are medium of comfort, coping up with stress in day-to-day life, or enhancing ultimate happiness. Here, the word perception signifies an opinion; it means a particular way of looking at or understanding something. Some people are thrilled to watch a comedy show while others are scared to even think about it as they have different views. This is because they can be very entertaining and provide people with a good laugh but at the same time, they can also be quite embarrassing and can affect an individual's mental health. An example of this is the stand-up comedy shows in which the comedian often defames and makes fun of person/persons in front of thousands of people. Moreover, Indian comedy shows are often based on stereotypes and exaggerated situations. These shows are of distinctive types as many comedians use vulgar or abusive language to make people laugh while some do healthy or

*Corresponding author: Ajay Kumar, Associate Professor, Department of Political Science, Ramanujan College, University of Delhi, Delhi, India.

clean comedies. That's why people have different perceptions of stand-up comedy and other comedy shows which are released at national television and YouTube especially in India. Just because of this cause the study about the happiness and people's perception towards standup comedy and other comedy shows in India is taken as a serious matter for investigation.

2. Review of Literature

2.1. Meaning of Happiness and its elements

Happiness is an enduring state of well-being involving satisfaction in the pleasant, good, and meaningful dimensions of life. Some psychologists believe that positive psychology is considered the science of happiness, which creates a difference between happiness and authentic happiness (well-being). The theory suggests that happiness can be described as three distinct elements opted for their own sake such as positive emotion, engagement, and meaning [2] [3]. Positive emotion is what we perceive or feel: pleasure, rapture, laughing, ecstasy, warmth, and comfort; a life led successfully around this crucial element is pleasant. When we go on a holiday, spend time with friends and watch our favorite TV shows, secure cherished promotions, or get a new job, we are easily in that element of positive emotion. Yet, this state is temporary and remains only until peoples yearn for bigger and better. Engagement is about being in flow or a bond: creative pursuits, competitive sport, writing, playing an instrument or watching TV shows or movies... pursuits where individuals lose their sense of time and their-self. In this state, the person often becomes a part of the action and cannot dissociate or even explain the element separately from themselves. This is the zone of individual creativity and concentration. Meaningfulness is always about someone else; an objective bigger than the self. A meaningful life involves a relation to and serving something that you accept is bigger than you. Although the potential of meaning is limitless, a small, local cause that serves the needy over a sustained period could be a meaningful pursuit [4] e.g. coping-up with stress, anxiety, and depression in the life. However, laughter is the best medicine to get stress relief. Thus, the fulfillment of purpose is part of authentic happiness.

2.2. Relationship of Humor with Happiness

Most people like humorous persons; basically humorists are entertaining, funny, energetic, and attractive. People cannot escape themselves from getting in touch with humor because it is commonly used every day. It seems in daily events, parties, and media (whether it is a comedy show or stand-up). It not only serves a social purpose but also strengthens people's abilities in coping-up with stress [5]. Ford, et al. (2016) observed the relationship of humor style with happiness [6]. According to Warren, et al. (2018), humor may refer to something that is intended to be funny [7]. According to Stern (1996), we cite the stimuli (gestures, behaviors, sayings, images, sounds, videos, etc.) that bring out or are intended to elicit laughter, amusement, or the perception that something is funny as a comedy [8]. Humor is not a stimulus, but a psychological reaction or response to a stimulus [9] [10] [11]. Comedy is not restricted to jokes but includes a vast range of behaviors: stand-up, cartoons, facial expressions, and tickle attacks, which may be communicated face-to-face, via print, traditional media, or increasingly, social media [12]. Similarly, the humor or comic sentiments sometimes derive from personal insults, social bigotry, sexual comments, and political satire, etc. Thus, stand-up and comedy shows oftentimes have comedians using, tickling, sexuality, sexual abuse, body-shaming, obscenity, racist comments, etc., to provide humor and to engage the audience by giving pleasure or happiness.

2.3. Comedy/Humor and Its Characteristics

Entertainment covers the activities which enable people to have a joyful time, particularly in their free time, and helps them relax and forget especially the current situation and their daily life scenarios. Thus, entertainment becomes very significant in our lives; it has always been an integral part of life. Entertaining activities can refresh people's minds and preserve their mental health as well as emotional well-being. It may bring happiness into their life. Some of these activities may even bring people closer to their friends and family members. Basically, entertainment fills people's life with happiness, there are various forms of entertainment, and currently in India emerging forms of entertainment is comedy shows on television and stand-up comedy on online platforms. Like entertainment, comedy is an integral part of our lives; psychologically comedy conveys the humor in our lives and in tough times when most people suffer from mental illness-related issues or stress and anxiety. It's safe to say that comedy works as dopamine to our body, and because of this, the comedy industry is in its boom.

Historically, stand-up comedy has been a crucial means of resistance or a tool for affecting change. This platform originates the purpose to challenge the dominant norms and upsetting the formal public discourse [13]. Perez (2013) argues that stand-up comedy often breaches the norms of etiquette and repeatedly highlights the significance of confronting burning subjects and issues that do not always get expression in politically repressed communities and societies [14]. Stand-up comedy is mostly used to articulate alternate opinions and to bring in the required

consciousness to oppose the dominant ideology [15]. Sophie Quirk, the author of the book *Why Stand-up Matters* asserts that “This process necessarily involves more than just an expression of the individual performer’s viewpoint. If we find a joke offensive, we protest by not laughing at it” [16].

There are many comedy shows such as *The Great Indian Laughter Challenge* which was the first stand-up comedy show on Indian television, and the *Kapil Sharma Show* which is currently quite popular; it is an Indian Hindi stand-up comedy and talk television series, apart from these many other are in this series such as *Bhabhiji Ghar par hain*, *Jijaji Chhatt par hain*, *Laugh India Laugh*, *Comedy Circus Ke Superstars*, *Comedy Open Mic*. Among these there are many popular shows; for instance, ‘*Comedy Open Mic*’ a stand-up comedy show, and ‘*The Kapil Sharma Show*. There are a few things that people keep in mind while watching such shows, whereas Indian comedy shows/serials are often based on stereotypes and exaggerated situations. These shows are of distinctive types as there are many comedians who use vulgarity or abusive language to make people laugh while some do healthy or clean comedies such as *Shrimaan Shrimati* and *Tarak Mehta Ka Ooltah Chasma*, a television series.

Standup comedy in India is still a very new concept for the mainstream Indian audience. With the rapid rise of internet penetration and shifting of a large number of television audiences to over-the-top (OTT) platforms and other digital streaming platforms like *YouTube* and *Instagram*, stand-up comedians in India are now getting an audience for their shows offline and online. Though a major portion of their audience is from the metro cities of the country, through digital mediums, Indian stand-up comedians, especially the Hindi stand-up comedians of the country, are becoming very popular. Comedy shows are not exactly a very new thing in India. Stand-up comedy used to happen earlier also, in which comedians like Johnny Lever, Dinesh Hingu and, etc were involved in the 1990s, but they did not become so popular then. However, earlier comedy acts were more fictional stories or imaginary scenes performed in a funny way in front of a large group of audience. Modern stand-up comedy acts are more into sharing one's life experiences, personal stories, and opinions or thoughts in a humorous way in front of a group of audiences. The introduction of standup comedy shows into the performing art scene of the country has given an opportunity to modern millennials to explore their hidden talents in comedy. Many online streaming platforms host shows featuring new-age Indian stand-up comedians. A large number of modern office-going millennials want to try their luck in stand-up comedy. Indian stand-up comedians are turning into modern offbeat celebrities among the millennials [17].

Stand-up comedy culture is not a very familiar concept for the Indian audience and even for the mainstream comedians of the country. The positive side of this is the flexibility of the new-age comedians of the country to try different styles and different topics and even experiment with sensible, religious, and controversial topics. India being a vibrant democracy is a home of various religious groups, different language-speaking people, and different races. Some of the stand-up comedians in India had to face a lot of criticism in recent years as *Twitter-trolling* because of their content based on religious events, beliefs, and races. Recently Agrima Joshua, a stand-up comedian from Lucknow has faced a lot of criticism because she remarked on Shivaji Maharaj. Kunal Kamra is known best for his sharp critique of the BJP-led government. These are just a few incidences where a comedian was brought into controversy because of his/her content. However, the usages of slang are very common now and nobody seems to have any problem with it. Stand-up comedy in India is all about storytelling and it's very normal to use some abusive or cuss words in front of an adult grown-up audience to make it feel more realistic.

Humor and entertainment have become evidently inherent in the emergent stand-up comedy. Various issues bordering on human relations, politics, religion, etc. have become the predominant context for standup comedies. Those issues are portrayed with the use of humor and satire significantly easier for the audience to intake as a means of entertainment but sometimes these become offensive for a few segments of society and create controversy.

Today, most people avoid to watching comedy shows with their family, especially stand-up comedy shows many researchers like Aatish Kapadia states that comedy has gotten vulgar nowadays by using double-meaning dialogues [18]. A lot of double-meaning dialogues are being used due to which the essence of real comedy is getting lost somewhere. Moreover, people also started liking such content and they laugh over it, they prefer such vulgar content over clean comedy because of which memes page on social media such as *Adult Gram*, *Qtiyapa*, and *Tharki Society* have millions of followers. Similarly, there are many comedy shows on Indian channels in which vulgar or sexual comments are used such as *Bhabhiji Ghar Par Hain*, *Happu ki Ultan Paltan*, and *Comedy Nights with Kapil*, (or *Kapil Sharma Show*) These shows are based on vulgarity and produced in an adult tone [19]. Since these serials are famous among families and children are also watching these shows. The dialogues are mostly not up to mark or have double-meaning and total vulgar language was used in these shows, such as *Double Bed*, *Hich-Hich awaaz*, *Nokdar Dhardar hal of Tiwariji*, *Rat ko Hal chalana hai Gulfam Kali ke khet main*, etc. are shameful and not able to digest by the Indian family especially inconsiderable for children. Basically, sexism was chosen as the tool to enhance the fun quotient in these kinds of shows [20].

Similarly, standup comedians on online platforms use teasing audiences by sharing content or experiences, they make fun of people who live in a particular city as “Delhi wale aise hote hai” or “hum to UP wale hain hamare yahan sab khulle mein hi hota hai”. Teasing sensibilities and raising feelings of discomfort among the audience are common practices in stand-up comedy, besides it they mock politicians. It should be noted that stand-up comedians use to speak English or Hindi on stage, both are typically mixed with words and phrases from the other language. This language mixture is also called *Hinglish*. Thus, they are promoting a new (immoral) language and spoiling the form of the mainstream languages by which these mainstream languages losing their importance in current society. The most popular satirical spectrums are *All India Bakchod*, *East India Comedy*, and *Aisi Taisi Democracy*. Mostly in standup and comedy shows in India, comedians joke about feminine hygiene products [21], sexism [22], obscenity [23], regional and casteist comments [24], political satire, and urban-rural divides to create humor in the audience but without any censorship [25].

3. Conceptual Framework

With reference to the review of literature, a conceptual framework model is proposed in Figure 1 to explain people’s perception towards Indian stand-up and comedy shows to attain happiness.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of the Study

3.1. Statement of Problem

People’s happiness is India’s concern for the past few years and now it has become an important concern for the country. Peoples largely depend upon stand-up and online and offline comedy shows regarding their fun and happiness. Therefore, it is too important to know the people’s perception regarding stand-up and comedy shows in India to get a stress-less life. While some people have the perception that these types of stand-up and comedy shows are corrupting society and are not worth watching. Hence, it is important to understand people’s perceptions regarding happiness through watching these kinds of shows.

3.2. Research Objectives

- To know the people’s perception towards stand-up and comedy shows to get happiness.
- To understand and evaluate the relationship between happiness’ characteristics and popular factors or contents of stand-up and comedy shows.
- To find out the factors affecting the people’s perception regarding these shows in terms of getting happiness.

3.3. Hypotheses

- H01: There is no relationship between people’s happiness and popular factors or contents of stand-up and comedy shows.

- H02: There is no impact of popular factors or contents of stand-up and comedy shows on people's happiness.

4. Material and method

The people's perception was assessed through an online survey. The online survey was carried out using Google forms. The current study utilizes the exploratory research methodology in exploring the extent of the impact and relationship between people's happiness (e.g. pleasure, laughing, comfort, funny, entertainment, amusement, removing anxiety and depression) and stand-up and comedy shows. A convenience sampling method was adopted to select the total sample size of 176 respondents consisting of 70 males and 106 females living in Delhi. The responses to the measurement were scored using a 5-point Likert scale. The measurement items of the variables were created on the basis of the literature review. The Regression and the Chi-square tests were used to test the hypotheses. Analysis of data and testing of hypotheses were performed by using SPSS software version 26.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Reliability analysis for variables

It is very crucial to know and understand whether there is internal consistency among the items in the different variables. Therefore, the result of the reliability analysis for all variables is shown in Table 1 below. The value of Cronbach's alpha is 0.791 which is above 0.70 for 25 items so data can be considered normal and reliable. Now we could apply a parametric test since the data is normal.

Table 1 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.791	25

5.2. Demographic Information

Table 2 Demographic Information

Characteristics	Description	Frequency	Percent
Age	18-25 Years	154	87.5
	26-30 Years	9	5.1
	31-40 Years	5	2.8
	41-50 Years	5	2.8
	50 and above	3	1.7
Gender	Male	70	39.8
	Female	106	60.2
Marital Status	Single	159	90.3
	Married	17	9.7
Educational Qualification	Higher Secondary	16	9.1
	Undergraduate	114	64.8
	Graduate	24	13.6
	Post-Graduate	14	8.0
	Others	8	4.5
Household Income (Monthly)	10000-20000 (INR)	56	31.8
	21000-30000 (INR)	28	15.9

	31000-50000 (INR)	43	24.4
	50000 (INR) and above	49	27.8
	Total	176	100.0

Table 2 is showing the majority of the respondents is females (60.2%) and can be found in the age category 18-25 years (87.5%). Most of them are undergraduate students (64.8%) and lastly in terms of monthly income, they earn 10000-20000 (INR) (31.8%) which is the lowest earning category.

5.3. The Relationship between variables affecting people's perception of standup and comedy shows regarding their happiness

Table 3 Chi-Square Test

	Pearson Chi-Square Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Results
Comedy shows or stand-up shows are watched for humor or fun. * Happiness	112.973 ^a	60	0.000	Rejected
Vulgar jokes make people laugh a lot. * Happiness	68.998 ^a	60	0.199	Supported
Abusive language is mostly used in stand-up comedy. * Happiness	54.762 ^a	45	0.151	Supported
Comedians consider personal insults or personal experiences as very good funny content while doing stand-up comedy. * Happiness	108.439 ^a	60	0.000	Rejected
Double-meaning jokes/expressions in comedy shows or stand-up comedy make people laugh a lot. * Happiness	100.306 ^a	60	0.001	Rejected
Body shaming and sexual comments are used more in stand-up comedy or comedy shows. * Happiness	98.222 ^a	60	0.001	Rejected
Viewers don't like to laugh at clean jokes in standup comedy or comedy shows * Happiness	56.830 ^a	60	0.592	Supported
Political satire is given more importance in standup comedy and comedy shows to intellectual viewers. * Happiness	88.526 ^a	60	0.010	Rejected
Racist /casteist comments are also made as laughing content of stand-up comedy or comedy shows. * Happiness	78.938 ^a	60	0.051	Supported
Stand-up comedy or comedy shows are incomplete without sexual comments. * Happiness	75.419 ^a	60	0.087	Supported
Stereotypes and exaggerations have also become a major part of fun-making content in stand-up and comedy shows. * Happiness	123.965 ^a	60	0.000	Rejected
Comedy shows or stand-up comedy helps in the conversion of negative thoughts into positive thoughts or creates optimism. * Happiness	135.123 ^a	60	0.000	Rejected

Here Pearson chi-square values' superscripts 'a' resembles a normalized sum of squared deviations between observed and theoretical frequencies

Table 3 shows the results of the chi-square tests for hypothesis H01 where we found the chi-square values are greater than 0.05 significant levels there we can say that the null hypothesis is supported at the 5% significant level which shows a negative association between happiness and popular factors or contents of stand-up and comedy shows.

Table 4 General Parameters for collecting response from the respondents

Parameters	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Comedy shows or stand-up shows are watched for humor or fun. * Happiness	2	2	14	114	44
Vulgar jokes make people laugh a lot. * Happiness	8	24	57	69	18
Abusive language is mostly used in stand-up comedy. * Happiness	0	19	49	84	24
Comedians consider personal insults or personal experiences as very good funny content while doing stand-up comedy. * Happiness	4	12	27	98	35
Double-meaning jokes/expressions in comedy shows or stand-up comedy make people laugh a lot. * Happiness	4	6	38	94	34
Body shaming and sexual comments are used more in stand-up comedy or comedy shows. * Happiness	6	33	39	79	19
Viewers don't like to laugh at clean jokes in stand-up comedy or comedy shows * Happiness	10	58	52	45	11
Political satire is given more importance in stand-up comedy and comedy shows to intellectual viewers. * Happiness	4	13	68	79	12
Racist /casteist comments are also made as laughing content of stand-up comedy or comedy shows. * Happiness	8	42	46	69	11
Stand-up comedy or comedy shows are incomplete without sexual comments. * Happiness	21	70	38	34	13
Stereotypes and exaggerations have also become a major part of fun-making content in stand-up and comedy shows. * Happiness	1	20	51	92	12
Comedy shows or stand-up comedy helps in the conversion of negative thoughts into positive thoughts or creates optimism. * Happiness	4	26	65	68	13

To explore the different characteristics of people's happiness regarding stand-up and comedy shows the data shows in the table 4:

- 89.7% of the respondents believe that comedy shows or stand-up shows are watched for humor or fun.
- 49.4% of the respondents believe that vulgar jokes make people laugh a lot.
- 61.3% of the respondents believe that abusive language is mostly used in standup comedy.
- 75.5% of the respondents believe that comedians consider personal insults or personal experiences as very good funny content while doing standup comedy.
- 72.7% of the respondents believe that double-meaning jokes/expressions in comedy shows or standup comedy make people laugh a lot.
- 55.6% of the respondents believe that body shaming and sexual comments are used more in standup comedy or comedy shows.
- 31.8% of the respondents believe that viewers don't like to laugh at clean jokes in standup comedy or comedy shows.
- 51.7% of the respondents believe that political satire is given more importance in standup comedy and comedy shows to intellectual viewers.

- 45.4% of the respondents believe that racist/casteist comments are also made as laughing content of standup comedy or comedy shows.
- 26.7% of the respondents believe that standup comedy or comedy shows are incomplete without sexual comments.
- 59.0% of the respondents believe that stereotypes and exaggerations have also become a major part of fun-making content in standup and comedy shows.
- 46.0% of the respondents believe that comedy shows or standup comedy helps in the conversion of negative thoughts into positive thoughts or creates optimism.

With the help of the statistical result, it can be concluded that people’s perception towards comedy shows and stand-up comedy in terms of attaining happiness can be measured with characteristics of the comedy shows and stand-up comedy e.g. double-meaning jokes/expressions, vulgarity, abusive language, body shaming, political satires, etc. The Chi-square test was used to test the relation between happiness and popular factors or contents of comedy shows and stand-ups to know the people’s perceptions regarding these shows. In the Chi-square table, data clearly shows that comedy shows or stand-up shows are watched for humor or fun to be happy and comedians consider personal insults or personal experiences as very good funny content while doing stand-up shows in which double-meaning jokes/expressions, abusive language, body shaming, political satires, stereotypes and exaggerations, and sexual comments are a very good mediums of attaining happiness or pleasure. Along with this, comedy shows or stand-up comedy helps in the conversion of negative thoughts into positive thoughts or creates optimism.

While a group of people believes that vulgar jokes and abusive language make people laugh a lot in comparison to clean jokes. Sometimes Racist or casteist, and sexual comments are also used to make people laugh (see table 4), which is very bad/immoral for a civilized society.

The regression coefficient ‘R’=0.612 or 61.2% means that the correlation between dependent variables and independent variables is positive. As a coefficient of determination R Square value is equal to 0.374 indicating that 37.4 % of the variation in dependent variables is explained by independent variables. The F test value of 8.122 is significant. Since the significance level is equal to 0.000 which is found less than 0.05. This also means that the correlation between dependent and independent variables is statistically significant and this regression model is valid.

As shown in table 5 the stepwise regression summary this shows only three factors among all the 12 factors affecting peoples’ perception regarding stand-up and comedy show contents positively related to their happiness. Hence, researchers reject the null hypothesis and concluded that there is sufficient evidence, at the 5% level of significance, that there is a strong positive relationship between people’s happiness and standup and comedy shows contents.

Table 5 a Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.612 ^a	0.374	0.328	2.52997

a. Predictors: (Constant), Optimism, Personal insults or personal experiences, Vulgar jokes, Abusive language, Humor or fun, Stereotypes and exaggerations, Clean jokes, Double-meaning jokes/expressions, Political satire, Racist /casteist comments, Sexual comments, Body shaming.

Table 5 b ANOVA Analysis

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	623.857	12	51.988	8.122	0.000 ^b
	Residual	1043.325	163	6.401		
	Total	1667.182	175			

a. Dependent Variable: Happiness

b. Predictors: (Constant), Optimism, Personal insults or personal experiences, Vulgar jokes, Abusive language, Humor or fun, Stereotypes and exaggerations, Clean jokes, Double-meaning jokes/expressions, Political satire, Racist /casteist comments, Sexual comments, Body shaming.

Table 5 c Coefficient Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta		
Model		B	Std. Error		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	13.308	1.813		7.340	0.000
	Comedy shows or stand-up shows are watched for humor or fun.	1.652	0.319	0.366	5.178	0.000
	Vulgar jokes make people laugh a lot.	-0.184	0.217	-0.059	-0.848	0.398
	Abusive language is mostly used in stand-up comedy.	-0.630	0.259	-0.174	-2.434	0.016
	Double-meaning jokes/expressions in comedy shows or stand-up comedy make people laugh a lot.	0.345	0.259	0.095	1.332	0.185
	Comedians consider personal insults or personal experiences as very good funny content while doing stand-up comedy.	0.317	0.250	0.092	1.269	0.206
	Body shaming and sexual comments are used more in stand-up comedy or comedy shows.	-0.335	0.241	-0.111	-1.390	0.167
	Viewers don't like to laugh at clean jokes in stand-up comedy or comedy shows	-0.007	0.227	-0.002	-0.031	0.976
	Political satire is given more importance in stand-up comedy and comedy shows to intellectual viewers.	0.085	0.280	0.023	0.306	0.760
	Racist /casteist comments are also made as laughing content of stand-up comedy or comedy shows.	0.092	0.232	0.030	0.396	0.692
	Stand-up comedy or comedy shows are incomplete without sexual comments.	0.211	0.214	0.077	0.983	0.327
	Stereotypes and exaggerations have also become a major part of fun-making content in stand-up and comedy shows.	0.356	0.298	0.093	1.193	0.235
	Comedy shows or stand-up comedy helps in the conversion of negative thoughts into positive thoughts or creates optimism.	0.922	0.244	0.269	3.778	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Happiness

The regression table clearly shows that people's happiness depends upon some crucial characteristics of the comedy shows and stand-up. For instant, humor or fun, abusive language and optimism creates too happiness in the peoples regarding comedy shows and standup comedy. It means these shows convert negative thoughts into positive thoughts or creates optimism that removes anxiety, stress and depression of the people. The study also shows that now clean jokes are very less used to make the audience laugh while people also still prefer them.

6. Conclusion

We may conclude that the study dealt with people's perception to feel happiness through comedy shows and stand-up comedy. It can be summarized from the above study that people's perception to feel happiness is positively associated

with the content part of comedy shows and stand-up. Peoples seek their happiness in these contents through watching these shows. Study shows that peoples think that racist or casteist, and sexual comments do not anymore become the medium of happiness while other contents of comedians like personal insults or personal experiences, double-meaning jokes/expressions, body shaming, political satires, stereotypes, and exaggerations-related comments become the medium of peoples' happiness or positive thoughts which remove anxiety, stress and depression of the society. Thus, this study tries to fulfill all the research objectives.

The limitation of the study is that it has taken only a few perspectives of people's perceptions regarding to attain their happiness related to comedy and standup shows. It is a data-based study and has been done with a survey from Delhi only in which mostly undergraduate female students participated and there is more scope to explore more areas in terms of this kind of study. The overall research suggests that the number of such contents should be increased in comedy shows or stand-up comedy so that people can get more happiness due to which people can get rid of mental diseases like anxiety, day-to-day stress of workload, and depression, and our society could be happier. A variety of clean jokes should be included and presented in a humorous style so that people prefer clean jokes also so that the decency of society is not hurt.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We are obliged and thankful for the support of our respondents, colleagues especially at Ramanujan College, family members, and all the authors and scholars who were cited in this work.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The researchers declared that there is no 'conflict of interest' in this manuscript publication.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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Author's short biography

Ajay Kumar, He is presently teaching at Ramanujan College (University of Delhi) Kalkaji, New Delhi, India as an Associate Professor in the Department of Political Science. He was awarded a Ph.D. by the Department of Political Science, University of Delhi. His areas of interest include International Relations and Dalit & Ambedkar Studies. He has published several books related to his areas of interest with reputed foreign publications like PEARSON and SAGE. He has several articles and book reviews to his credit in various national and international peer-reviewed and Scopus indexed journals. He has teaching and research experience of 15 years. He has presented many papers at conferences both at home and abroad.

Sofiya Khan & Tanushka Soni. They are studying at Ramanujan College and are involved in several minor research projects. They have been involved in this research paper as Project Assistants on behalf of the Department of Political Science, Ramanujan College, University of Delhi, Delhi, India.